

The Searching for the Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP and the Chinese top cities GDP analysis Sustainably through Observing Historical Statistic Value

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ABSTRACT: The nations & regions' GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economic growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapidly developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So, we judge the economy developing enhancement and decrease through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained in a low economic situation, but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously specially by scientists, senior engineers, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into realizing new-quality productivity producing a certain effectiveness to GDP enhancement as last. In the meantime,

The new-high-technology product will be formed accordingly that can create the industrial chains to support the high-knowledge skill transformed into the more comprehensive and complicated product for the sake of serving our citizen with modernization. The emerging technology would drive the new energy force that includes the low -carbon and low-contamination electricity generator which may form the new quality productivity protecting our earth from carbon-oxide and nitric-oxide etc. release. So that some high-tech products would be aware that the transformation positively prepares the futural product producing and application. Thereby, the nation's GDP will reflect the whole economy special in new high-tech-field makers, and products will play a significant influence on that value increasement and control the y-y value under our consideration.

Keywords: *Searching for; analyzing; Chinese top cities; Mumbai & Chinese Zhejiang cities; by sustainably observing.*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economic growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapidly developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So, we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP, which indicates national economic status, has provided an important role in every aspect of the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence, we should consider the effective factors, for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high technique etc. like big plane, electric vehicle battery, AI robot, quantum computer, medicine making, disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence).

ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enabled to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So, the certain population is about to improve our national confidence to some degree and make us become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rates mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various backgrounds and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation, the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years' experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modern. An innovative industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommending the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~20]

2. Discussions

2.1 Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP analysis

The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities' GDP would show 3 billion dollars by Jiaxing~Ningbo cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 1 in 1980. The y-y value in 1980 might exhibit 1.1% by them showing their slower growth step.

Figure 1. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP I. [1]

The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 49~4.5 billion dollars by Mumbai~Hangzhou cities indicated the Mumbai capital forward economy strength in terms of Figure 2 in 1980. The y-y value in 1980 might exhibit 6%~14% by them showing the Hangzhou city faster growth step.

Figure 2. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP II. [1]

The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 2~1.5 billion dollars by Jinhua~Taizhou cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 3 in 1980. The y-y value in 1980 might exhibit 0.5%~-1.3% by them showing their slowest growth step.

Figure 3. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP III. [1]

At the end, the Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 14~7 billion dollars by Hangzhou~Jiaxing cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 4 in 1987. The y-y value in 1980 might exhibit 34%~16% by them showing their slowest growth step.

Figure 4. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP III. [1]

1.2 Chinese top cities GDP analysis

The Chinese top cities GDP analysis 6~3 billion dollars by Shanghai~Beijing cities accordingly in 1984 exhibited their forward economy strength in light of Figure 5. The y-y value would indicate 16%~20% respectively realized their more forward growth steps.

Figure 5 The Chinese top cities GDP analysis [2]

The Chinese top cities GDP analysis 2~1 billion dollars by Tianjin~Chengdu cities accordingly in 1984 exhibited their weak economy strength in light of Figure 6. The y-y value would indicate 18%~20% respectively realized their more forward growth steps.

Figure 6 The Chinese top cities GDP analysis I [2]

3. Conclusions

The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economic growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapidly developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So, we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained in a low economic situation, but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously specially by scientists, senior engineers, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into realizing new-quality productivity producing a certain effectiveness to GDP enhancement as last. In the meantime, the new-high-technology product will be formed accordingly that can create the industrial chains to support the high-knowledge skill transformed into the more comprehensive and complicated product for the sake of serving our citizen with modernization. The emerging technology would drive the new energy force that includes the low -carbon and low-contamination electricity generator which may form the new quality productivity protecting our earth from carbon-oxide and nitric-oxide etc. release. So that some high-tech products would be aware that the transformation positively prepares the futural product producing and application. Thereby, the nation's GDP will reflect the whole economy special in new high-tech-field makers, and products will play a significant influence on that value increasement and control the y-y value under our consideration.

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